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Professional Competencies and Job Performance of Select Academic Librarians in Laguna, Philippines

Objective. Academic libraries formulate missions, visions, goals, and objectives based on the aims of the parent organization. There are issues with how librarianship is introduced, particularly in post-generation Z, when individuals have misconceptions about the functions of librarians. This study examined the level of professional competencies and job performance of selected academic librarians in the 21st Century. **Methods.** Descriptive-correlation method of research was used to provide static pictures of situations as well as to establish relationship between different variables. The respondents of this study are selected academic librarians in region IV-A Philippines. **Results.** Findings revealed that majority of respondents were 31 years old and above and were female. Meanwhile, the majority of the respondents attained their bachelor's degree and had been in the service for 10 years and below. The academic librarians are highly competent in managing information technologies among three domains of professional competencies. The academic librarians achieve very high level of job performance maintaining high quantity of work, fulfilling job duties, consistent for high quality of work, respond to the needs of users, provide accurate resources, demonstrate responsiveness, are able to use technology, and actively participate in forums. The academic librarians aged 31 years old and above, with master's degree and have 11 years and above of service, higher level of professional competencies than their younger counterpart, with bachelor's degree and 10 years and below of service. The higher the respondents' level of professional competencies in all its dimensions, the higher the level of respondent's job performance. **Conclusions.** It can be concluded that the majority of academic librarians in this study were female, 31 years old and above. They had a bachelor's degree and 10 years or less of service. Academic librarians showed high competence in managing information technologies and consistently performed well in their job duties. Older librarians with a master's degree and over 11 years of service displayed higher professional competency and job performance compared to younger librarians with a bachelor's degree and less than 10 years of service. There was a positive correlation between professional competencies and job performance. Overall, academic librarians in this study exhibited strong professional competencies and high job performance.

Keywords: academic librarians; professional competency; job performance; Philippines

Introduction

The Commission on Higher Education (n.d.) and accrediting organizations set requirements for libraries in the Philippines. Standards have also been set by organizations that promote libraries, such as the Philippine Association of Academic and Research Librarians (PAARL). Congruently, the Professional Regulation Commission's (PRC) Board for Librarians (BFL) has produced a set of requirements for academic, public, special, and school libraries (Obille, 2007).

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Members of the Board for Librarians (BFL) and academic librarians agreed that professional competencies should be formalized into model statements based on the four domains of the Special Library Association (SLA) model known as the Competencies for Information Professionals of the Twenty-First Century. The National Competency-Based Standards for Librarians NCBSL was prescribed, adopted and promulgated on June 26, 2015.

Fig. 1. NCBSL Model

Visible abilities such as knowledge and skills may be somewhat technical competencies that are essentially required by the job and drive an individual's job performance (Vathanophas, 2007). Older employees were shown to have statistically significant higher job engagement than younger employees, which was discovered to be higher in absorption and dedication (Douglas & Roberts, 2020). Younger workers perform differently than older employees in a particular job. According to Ugwu (2017), only age, education, and job experience were determined to be significant of librarian's task-based performance.

Problem Statement

Librarians must comprehend the structure, organization, creation, management, dissemination, usage, and preservation of new and existing information resources in all formats. Having developed appropriate knowledge and skills, the librarian becomes an asset to the organization. But, how do we measure the librarians' competencies that reside outside of the National Capital Region? While this is not a comparative study, it explores the current status of professional competencies of librarians situated outside of Manila.

Specifically, it will answer the following sub-problems:

1. What is the profile of respondents in terms of:
 - a. Age
 - b. Sex
 - c. Highest educational attainment; and
 - d. Length of service as a librarian

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2. What is the respondents' level of professional competencies in terms of:
 - a. Managing information sources
 - b. Managing information services
 - c. Managing information technologies; and
 - d. Managing information organization
3. What is the respondents' level of job performance?
4. Is there a significant difference in the respondents' level of professional competencies when grouped according to their profile variables?
5. Is there a significant difference in the respondents' level of job performance when grouped according to their profile variables?
6. Is there a significant relationship between the respondents' level of professional competencies and level of job performance?

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on the Self-Determination Theory: How It Explains Motivation by Garraido (2023). The term self-determination was first introduced by Deci and Ryan in their 1985 book *Self-Determination and Intrinsic Motivation in Human Behavior*. People can become self-determined when they fulfill the needs for competence, autonomy, and relatedness.

Table 1

Self-determination Components

Competence	The necessity of having a sense of agency and being the one to take the initiative.
Autonomy	The need to have a sense of choice and be the initiator of an action
Relatedness	The requirement to develop mutual respect and reliance with people

This theory is aligned with the present study as it focuses on the four domains of professional competencies such as: managing information resources, managing information services, managing information tools and technology, and managing information organization that needs to be fulfilled to achieve a high level of competency which may lead to having a high level of job performance. Once competency is achieved, autonomy and relatedness will follow.

Methods

The researchers utilized the descriptive-correlation method of research to answer the specific questions. It describes the respondents' profile in terms of: age; gender; highest

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educational attainment; and length of service as a librarian, the professional competencies, and job performance of academic librarians. The self-made questionnaire was based on the National Competency-Based Standards for Filipino Librarians by the Professional Regulatory Commission (PRC).

The following statistical tools were used in the study: 1.) Frequency and percentage distribution were used to describe the profile of the respondents. 2.) Weighted mean was used to describe the respondents' level of professional competencies and level of job performance. 3.) T-test was used to describe the difference in the respondents' level of professional competencies and level of job performance when grouped according to their age, gender and length of service. 4.) Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to describe the difference in the respondents' level of professional competencies and level of job performance when grouped according to their highest educational attainment. 5.) Pearson r Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to determine the relationship between the respondents' level of professional competencies and level of job performance.

This study involved one hundred twelve (112) out of 157 active academic librarians who are currently working in Laguna. The sample size was calculated using a Raosoft calculator with a 95% confidence level and a 5% margin of error. The researcher used a random sampling method as it covered only 112 selected academic librarians who represent the whole number of the population.

The researchers used Google forms to distribute the floating questionnaire. The data were completed after a month of data collection process, collected, tabulated, and statistically treated under the supervision of the researchers' statistician.

The results from the self-made questionnaire are tallied in an Excel file. The mean was computed to determine the numerical range to interpret the data.

Table 2

Professional Competency's Categorical Response and Verbal Interpretation

Assigned Point	Numerical Range	Categorical Response	Verbal Interpretation
4	3.25-4.00	Strongly Agree	Highly competent
3	2.50-3.24	Agree	Competent
2	1.75-2.49	Disagree	Low competent
1	1.00-1.74	Strongly Disagree	Least competent

This table is the basis for data interpretation after determining the mean of the four domains of professional competencies.

Table 3

Job Performance's Categorical Response and Verbal Interpretation

Assigned Point	Numerical Range	Categorical Response	Verbal Interpretation
4	3.25-4.00	Strongly Agree	Very High
3	2.50-3.24	Agree	High
2	1.75-2.49	Disagree	Low
1	1.00-1.74	Strongly Disagree	Very Low

This table is the basis for data interpretation after determining the mean of the four domains of job performance.

Review of Related Literature

The development of National Competency-based Standards for Filipino Librarians is regarded as an essential component of the Continuing Professional Development of all registered and licensed librarians (CPD). Competency-based standards will describe the essential qualities necessary of a professional practicing librarianship. Professional competencies must be constructed into model statements that pertain to the four domains of the SLA model, which are categorized as follows: managing information resources; managing information services; managing information tools and technologies; and managing information organization (Verzosa, 2013).

Sutton and Collinge (2018) stated that there are some basic competencies that librarians of electronic resources must possess, including technical proficiency, understanding of the life cycle of e-resources, and the ability to do research and assessment, which relates to the competencies of academic and public electronic librarians.

Traditional skills are a strength of librarians. Yet, librarians should also be knowledgeable about non-traditional competencies. Contemporary LIS practitioners should be proactive; they should be strong communicators, competent, adaptable, and willing to support topics vital to librarianship practice. Indexing, abstracting, categorizing, and cataloging are examples of traditional skills. Non-traditional skills include technology, educational, and communication talents. It outlines the characteristics that a librarian in today's LIS business should have (Santos, 2018).

The study by Friday and Onuh (2022), found that librarians gained 21st-century librarianship abilities such as emailing, word processing, internet browsing, digital literacy, and social networking. Yet, Anthonia et al. (2021) discovered that information professionals such as librarians have a significant need for interpersonal, leadership, and information technology abilities in 21st-century libraries. Furthermore, Adomi and Solomon (2019) discovered that the majority of librarians from chosen colleges had a high level of customer service competency in terms of information and communication technologies, as well as professional and interpersonal competency.

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According to the study by Mandal and Dasgupta (2019), librarians can offer better service to the material available online by employing their search abilities. Participating in training programs, seminars and conferences and even other forms of continuing education is the key to developing their ever-changing professional ability. In light of the continually changing nature of their professions, the study shows that younger libraries are already professionals in current technologies, retaining their professional competence. Competence is an ever-evolving issue since it must adapt to societal changes. While working on information, technology, and services, library and information professionals have the same societal developments to contend with. Also, knowledge and skill should be relevant to the demands of the institution to be serviced (Alenzuela, Cantel, & Peleña, 2020).

Table 4

Profile of Respondents

FINDINGS/RESULTS

Profile Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Age		
30 years old and below	55	49.1
31 years old and above	57	50.9
Gender		
Male	28	25.0
Female	84	75.0
Highest Educational Attainment		
Bachelor's Degree	79	70.5
Master's Degree	31	27.7
Doctoral Degree	2	1.8
Length of Service		
10 years and below	75	67.0
11 years and above	37	33.0
N=112		

This table shows the frequency and percentage of the respondents according to their profile. The majority of the respondents were 31 years old and above. There were more females than males. The majority of the respondents attained their bachelor's degree. Meanwhile, the 10 years and below of service have the most number of respondents than 11 years and above.

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Table 5

Respondents' Level of Professional Competencies: Managing Information Sources

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. I manage the process by which library resources are selected and acquired.	3.55	Highly Competent	4
2. I understand the general structure, relationships and relative importance of library catalog systems and software (Classification Systems, e.g., LC, Dewey; subject headings List, e.g., LCSH, AACR2; RDA).	3.84	Highly Competent	1
3. I understand the acquisition and collection development processes and policies of the library.	3.82	Highly Competent	2
4. I use common social networking and online collaboration tools (e.g., blogs, podcasts, instant messaging tools, photo-sharing tools, web conferencing programs).	3.06	Competent	5
5. I understand preservation and conservation issues, including requirements for archival preservation and proper handling of materials.	3.62	Highly Competent	3
Overall Weighted Mean	3.59	Highly Competent	

As presented in Table 5, an average weighted mean of 3.59 showed that the respondents are highly competent in understanding the general structure, relationships, and relative importance of library catalog systems and software; understanding the acquisition and collection development processes and policies of the library; understanding preservation and conservation issues, including requirements for archival preservation and proper handling of materials; and managing the process by which the library resources are selected and acquired. But they are competent when using common social networking and online collaboration tools.

Table 6

Respondents' Level of Professional Competencies: Managing Information Services

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. I understand and perform the basic operations of the circulation function.	3.91	Highly Competent	1

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2. I explain and perform intra and interlibrary loan procedures, document delivery, resources sharing, reserves, and other information retrieval options.	3.42	Highly Competent	3
3. I understand the essential characteristics of reference service in order to assist, advice and instruct users in the use of primary resources.	3.66	Highly Competent	2
4. I develop and implement training programs to educate the library users on the use of the library and its resources.	3.29	Highly Competent	4
5. I develop, design, implement and asses the library's information literacy program.	3.25	Highly Competent	5
Overall Weighted Mean	3.51	Highly Competent	

As presented in Table 6, an average weighted mean of 3.51 showed that the respondents are highly competent in managing information services: performing the basic operations of the circulation function; understanding the essential characteristics of reference services to assist, advice, and instruct users in the use of primary resources and; performing intra and interlibrary loan procedures, document delivery, resource sharing, reserves, and other information retrieval options; developing and implementing programs; and developing, designing, implementing, and assessing the library's information literacy program.

Table 7

Respondents' Level of Professional Competencies: Managing Information Technologies

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. I perform basic functions of e-mail applications.	3.95	Highly Competent	1
2. I perform basic calendar and task management operations/applications.	3.88	Highly Competent	2
3. I understand and use basic computer hardware and peripherals.	3.60	Highly Competent	5
4. I understand common security protocols related to internet use.	3.66	Highly Competent	4
5. I understand and perform basic operating system functions (log on/off, launch programs from the desktop, use multiple windows, delete files).	3.75	Highly Competent	3

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As presented in Table 7, an average weighted mean of 3.77 showed that the respondents are highly competent in performing basic functions of e-mail applications; performing basic calendar and task management operations/applications and; performing basic operating system functions (log on/off, launches programs from desktop, uses multiple windows, delete files).

Table 8

Respondents' Level of Professional Competencies: Managing Information Organization

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. I envision strategic directions of the library in support of the programs of the institutions to which it is attached.	3.47	Highly Competent	2
2. I establish effective financial management processes and services, using sound business and financial judgement.	3.05	Competent	5
3. I employ sound project management principles and procedures in the planning and implementation of projects, programs and research.	3.13	Competent	4
4. I build effective and harmonious work relationships and personal growth of the people working within the organization.	3.62	Highly Competent	1

As presented in Table 8, an average weighted mean of 3.32 showed that the respondents are highly competent in building effective and harmonious work relationships and personal growth of the people working within the organization; envisioning strategic directions of the library in support of the programs of the institutions and; partnerships, within and outside the organization, to optimize use of library resources, promote library cooperation initiatives and ensure conformity with regulatory standards, laws and other policies affecting libraries.

Table 9

Summary Table of the Respondents' Level of Professional Competencies: Managing Information Sources, Managing Information Services, Managing Information Technologies, and Managing Information Organization

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Managing information sources	3.58	Highly Competent	2
2. Managing information services	3.51	Highly Competent	3
3. Managing information technologies	3.77	Highly Competent	1

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4. Managing information organization	3.32	Highly Competent	4
Overall Weighted Mean	3.55	Highly Competent	

As presented in Table 9, an average weighted mean of 3.55 showed that the respondents are highly competent in managing information technologies. This indicated that regardless of their age, highest educational attainment, and length of service, academic librarians are competent enough to perform their duties effectively.

Table 10

Respondents' Level of Job Performance

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. I maintain a high quantity of work output.	3.91	Very High	3.5
2. I take responsibility for fulfilling job duties.	3.91	Very High	3.5
3. I am demonstrating consistently high-quality work.	3.92	Very High	2
4. I quickly respond to the needs of internal and external clients.	3.72	Very High	5
5. I provide an accurate resource based on what patrons are looking for.	3.94	Very High	1
6. I demonstrate a responsiveness to the needs of internal and external clients.	3.65	Very High	7
7. I am able to use technology to access information.	3.71	Very High	6
8. I am able to create & explain the library's IT policies.	3.14	High	10
9. I know how to develop and manage the library's content management system.	3.27	High	9
10. I actively participate in or cooperate with the forums in my organization towards the development of the library.	3.54	Very High	8
Overall Weighted Mean	3.67	Very High	

As shown in Table 10, academic librarians rated themselves in job performance as "Very high," with an average weighted mean of 3.67. It appeared that they were very high in providing an accurate resource based on what patrons are looking for (Rank 1) with a weighted mean of 3.94; in demonstrating consistently high-quality work (Rank 2) with a weighted mean of 3.92; they also rated themselves as very high with the same weighted mean of 3.91 in maintaining a high quantity of work output and taking responsibility for fulfilling job duties (Rank 3.5). Likewise, they were

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very high in quick response to the needs of internal and external clients (Rank 5) with a weighted mean of 3.72; in using technology to access information (Rank 6) with a weighted mean of 3.71; same as in demonstrating a responsiveness to the needs of internal and external clients (Rank 7) with a weighted mean of 3.65; and in actively participating in or cooperate with the forums in organization towards the development of the library (Rank 8) with a weighted mean of 3.54; they also had high level in developing and managing the library's content management system (Rank 9) with a weighted mean of 3.27; and creating and explaining the library's IT policies (Rank 10) with a weighted mean of 3.14.

Table 11

Difference in the Respondents' Level of Professional Competencies When Grouped According to their Profile Variables

Profile Variables		Mean	Inferential Statistics	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Age	30 years old and below	3.38	t=-7.634	.000*	H ₀ rejected	Significant
	31 years old and above	3.70				
Gender	Male	3.49	t=-1.264	.213	H ₀ not rejected	Not Significant
	Female	3.56				
Highest Educational Attainment	Bachelor's Degree	3.47	F=13.838	.000*	H ₀ rejected	Significant
	Master's Degree	3.72				
	Doctoral Degree	3.87				
Length of service	10 years and below	3.44	t=-8.083	.000*	H ₀ rejected	Significant
	11 years and above	3.75				

As presented in Table 11, for the difference in the respondents' level of professional competencies when grouped according to their age (t=-7.634), highest educational attainment (F=13.838), and length of service (t=-8.083), the obtained p-values were all .000, respectively,

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which were all lower than the test of significance at .05, suggesting that there is enough statistical evidence to reject the null hypothesis which implies a significant difference. This means that those respondents aged 31 years old and above, with a master's degree and 11 years and above of service have a higher level of professional competencies than their younger counterparts, with a bachelor's degree and 10 years and below of service. Meanwhile, there is no significant difference in professional competencies according to their gender ($t=1.264$) which shows that no matter if you are a male or female, you can attain a high level of professional competencies as an academic librarian.

Table 12

Difference in the Respondents' Level of Job Performance When Grouped According to their Profile Variables

Profile Variables		Mean	Inferential Statistics	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Age	30 years old and below	3.38	$t=-7.634$.000*	H_0 rejected	Significant
	31 years old and above	3.70				
Gender	Male	3.65	$t=-.546$.588	H_0 not rejected	Not Significant
	Female	3.68				
Highest Educational Attainment	Bachelor's Degree	3.63	$F=4.738$.011*	H_0 rejected	Significant
	Master's Degree	3.78				
	Doctoral Degree	3.65				
Length of service	10 years and below	3.62	$t=-4.198$.000*	H_0 rejected	Significant

As presented in Table 12, using the T-test, the difference in the respondents' level of job performance when grouped according to their age is $t=-7.634$ and length of service $t=-4.198$. Using Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), the difference in the respondents' level of job performance according to their highest educational attainment is $F=4.738$. The obtained p-values were .000, .011, and .000, respectively, which were all lower than the test of significance at .05, suggesting that there is enough statistical evidence to reject the null hypothesis which implies a significant difference.

Table 13

Relationship between the Respondents' Level of Professional Competencies and Level of Job Performance

Job Performance	Inferential Statistics	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Managing information sources	r=.581 (moderate correlation)	.000*	Null Hypothesis Rejected	Significant
Managing information services	r=.536 (moderate correlation)	.000*	Null Hypothesis Rejected	Significant
Managing information technologies	r=.661 (moderate correlation)	.000*	Null Hypothesis Rejected	Significant
Managing information organization	r=.538 (moderate correlation)	.000*	Null Hypothesis Rejected	Significant
*Significant @ 0.01				

As presented in Table 13, the relationship between the respondents' level of performance and their level of professional competencies in terms of managing information sources ($r=.581$), managing information services ($r=.536$), managing information technologies ($r=.661$) and managing information organization ($r=.538$) show that all the obtained r-values indicated moderate correlation. Meanwhile, the p-values obtained were all .000, which was lower than the test of significance at .01 implying that there is enough statistical evidence to reject the null hypothesis, showing a significant relationship between the variables. This means that the higher the respondents' level of professional competencies in all its dimensions, the higher the level of respondents' job performance.

Results and Discussion

Self-determination is the idea that people are driven to engage in activities that need the fulfillment of competence, autonomy, and relatedness to achieve them. Having highly competent academic librarians can identify that they fulfill what is needed, which leads them to attain a high level of job performance.

It is noticeable that academic librarians have an advanced grasp of information technology and tools as they all recorded a high level of competency. Academic librarians showed self-determination to achieve competence, autonomy, and relatedness. Generally, academic librarians

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are highly competent in the four areas of professional competencies: managing information sources, managing information services, managing information technologies, and managing information organization. These competencies helped them to attain a highly competent job performance.

The findings revealed a remarkable level of proficiency among respondents in various aspects of their roles, particularly in the management of information technology, which garnered the highest average weighted mean of 3.77, securing the top rank. Following closely was the adept handling of information sources, with an average weighted mean of 3.58, earning the second position. Concurrently, the management of information services exhibited a commendable performance, achieving an average weighted mean of 3.51 and securing the third rank. Meanwhile, the management of information organization claimed the fourth position with an average weighted mean of 3.32.

An insightful observation derived from the results indicates that respondents aged 31 years old and above, possessing master's degrees, and boasting 11 years or more of service, demonstrated elevated levels of professional competencies compared to their younger counterparts. This implies that experience and advanced education play pivotal roles in enhancing professional capabilities within the realm of academic librarianship.

Notably, gender proved to be a negligible factor, as both males and females exhibited the potential to attain a high level of professional competencies as academic librarians. The data on professional competence, irrespective of age, educational background, and length of service, underscored the notion that academic librarians excel in their duties effectively. These results imply a universality of competence among academic librarians, emphasizing the inclusive nature of professional success in this field.

The select academic librarians meet the library professional's standards and competencies, which they are *highly competent* in terms of managing information tools and technology with an average of 3.77. This finding corroborates the study by Oza and Mehta (2018) which states that ICT skills and competencies are essential for corporate librarians and LIS professionals. Corporate librarians may perform a variety of roles, such as knowledge engineer, knowledge creator, information architect, web designer, database and network creator, online publisher, and decision support specialist.

Conclusions

Knowledge and skills have an impact on how others perceive you as a professional. Select academic librarians are determined as highly competent which serves as one step toward introducing this type of profession, which will lead to fewer misconceptions about the role of librarians. As they are attaining a high level of competency and job performance, it is concluded that they are ready for the job as professionals. In this regard, taking part in training courses, conferences, seminars, and other forms of ongoing education is essential to helping them build their ever-growing professional potential. For the future researcher, it is recommended to determine the level of competency and job performance of other types of librarians (public librarian, special librarian, school librarian).

Majority of them were 31 years old and above and were female. Meanwhile, the majority of the respondents attained their bachelor's degree and had been in the service for 10 years and below.

The academic librarians are highly competent in managing information technologies among three domains of professional competencies. The academic librarians are achieving a very

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high level of job performance, maintaining high quantity of work, fulfilling job duties, consistent for high quality of work, responding to the needs of users, providing accurate resources, demonstrating responsiveness, able to use technology, and actively participate in forums. The academic librarians aged 31 years old and above, with master's degree and have 11 years and above of service have higher level of professional competencies than their younger counterparts, with bachelor's degree and 10 years and below of service. The academic librarians aged 31 years old and above, with master's degree and have 11 years and above of service have higher level of job performance than their younger counterparts, with bachelor's degree and 10 years and below of service. The higher the respondents' level of professional competencies in all its dimensions, the higher the level of respondents' job performance.

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Професійні компетентності та ефективність роботи окремих академічних бібліотекарів у Лагуні, Філіппіни

Мета. Академічні бібліотеки формують місії, бачення, цілі та завдання на основі цілей материнської організації. Існують проблеми з тим, як впроваджувати бібліотечну справу, особливо серед представників покоління Z, коли люди мають хибні уявлення про функції бібліотекарів. У цьому дослідженні розглянуто рівень професійної компетентності та ефективність роботи окремих академічних бібліотекарів у 21 столітті. **Методика.** Описово-кореляційний метод дослідження для створення статичної картини ситуацій, а також для встановлення взаємозв'язку між різними змінними. Респондентами цього дослідження були обрані академічні бібліотекарі з регіону IV-A Філіппін. **Результати.** Результати опитування показали, що більшість респондентів були у віці 31 рік і старше і були жінками. При цьому більшість респондентів отримали ступінь бакалавра і мають стаж роботи 10 років і менше. Серед трьох сфер професійної компетентності академічні бібліотекарі мають високу компетентність в управлінні інформаційними технологіями. Академічні бібліотекарі досягають дуже високого рівня виконання роботи, підтримуючи високий обсяг роботи, виконуючи посадові обов'язки, послідовно забезпечуючи високу якість роботи, реагуючи на потреби користувачів, надаючи точні ресурси, демонструючи чуйність, вміння користуватися технологіями та беручи активну участь у форумах. Академічні бібліотекарі у віці 31 рік і старші, які мають ступінь магістра і стаж роботи 11 років і більше, мають вищий рівень професійних компетентностей, ніж їхні молодші колеги, які мають ступінь бакалавра і стаж роботи 10 років і менше. Академічні бібліотекарі віком 31 рік і старші, які мають ступінь магістра і стаж роботи 11 років і більше, мають вищий рівень виконання роботи, ніж їхні молодші колеги, які мають ступінь бакалавра і стаж роботи 10 років і менше. Чим вищий рівень професійних компетентностей респондентів за всіма вимірами, тим вищий рівень виконання роботи респондентами. **Висновки.** Можна зробити висновок, що більшість академічних бібліотекарів у цьому дослідженні були жінками, віком від 31 року. Вони мали ступінь бакалавра і стаж роботи не більше 10 років. Академічні бібліотекарі продемонстрували високу компетентність в управлінні інформаційними технологіями і стабільно

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добре виконували свої посадові обов'язки. Бібліотекарі старшого віку, які мають ступінь магістра і стаж роботи понад 11 років, продемонстрували вищий рівень професійної компетентності та виконання посадових обов'язків порівняно з молодими бібліотекарями, які мають ступінь бакалавра і стаж роботи менше 10 років. Існує позитивна кореляція між професійною компетентністю та ефективністю роботи. Загалом, академічні бібліотекарі в цьому дослідженні продемонстрували сильні професійні компетентності та високу ефективність роботи.

Ключові слова: академічні бібліотекарі; професійна компетентність; ефективність роботи; Філіппіни

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